

ISic0001

Funerary inscription

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

sarcophagus (lid)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Caltanissetta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 3501

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis · man(ibus)

2. Zethi

3. vixit · a(nnis) · VI

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491696

EDCS 21900531

Bibliography

Castelli, Gabriello Lancellotto, Principe di Torremuzza 1784. Siciliae et
objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio prolegomenis et

notis illustrata, et iterum cum emendationibus, & auctariis evulgata. Palermo.
At cl.14 no.147

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7190 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 1

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